

TEACHING ETHICS OF WATER USE IN WATER ECONOMY

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Abstract. Current work of analyst and otuv hadjaligida Suwan folgirendanish-etikaseli ura-leikatoni. Narodotourist leadership and Global suv cooperation, irrigation and drainage Commission and Orl dengizi and Volbondy on the territory of Uchun special Trust foundation, suv khujaligida of auxiliary significance. Dilalar and shvchilar uchnsya_ both times were present at the ethylgan proposal.

Keywords: Agriculture, International Water Resources holiday, Snellen shrift, water management, CUV ethics, energy supply, International Geological program, Koli-index, Vestas Wind Systems A/S

INTRODUCTION. In the languages of the peoples of Central Asia, there is a proverb "KUV zar-suvchi zargar". In English, there is also a proverb "water, water everywhere and do not drink", which means that water should be used as sparingly as possible[2]. In the culture of all peoples of the world, there are various proverbs about water and its reasonable use. March 22 has been celebrated worldwide by the UN General Assembly as an international water day since 1993. The national holiday "a drop of water is equal to gold" has been held in Turkmenistan since 1995 on the first Sunday of April. The two UN Water Conventions of 1992 and 1997, which are the framework instruments for international water cooperation, can serve as such instruments.

The main part. Irrigated agriculture is growing in many countries around the world as a result of farmers not paying the full cost of it for their use. Agricultural irrigation accounts for about 70% of the world's water use and more than 40% in

many OECD countries. Heavy use of underground pumps for irrigation can lead to negative environmental impacts on aquifers and cause significant economic impacts in the industry and beyond. In addition, agriculture is the main source of water pollution[3].

The problems of transboundary water use in the Central Asian region have become an important part of the environmental, social and economic problems in the relations of the States of the region. Modern water use in Central Asia does not correspond to the principle of sustainable water use. Inefficient use of water resources, pollution of water bodies and their degradation reduce the level of safety of the population from the impact of the water factor, lead to an increase in the cost of construction and protection of water bodies. The ongoing reforms in the field of agriculture and the current environmental situation require a new approach to state regulation of the formation of the water management system, reproduction and protection of water bodies while achieving sustainable water use parameters. Water management is an important component of the national water policy, and the formation of an adequate management system from the point of view of sustainable water management becomes an important task. At the same time, water management is understood as a set of measures and directions of the impact of a specially created state system on the socio-ecological and economic system of the basin. The growth of anthropogenic pressure on agroecosystems and the deterioration of water quality and the condition of reservoirs have a significant impact on the efficiency of the functioning of the multi-sectoral water management complex, worsen the living conditions and health of the population. The growing scale of irrational water use, taking into account the current and future development against the background of limited water resources, creates a number of environmental problems. Agriculture is the most water-intensive branch of the national economy. Difficulties in implementing structural changes in agriculture increase the negative impact of industry on the environment and public health. The level of use of land and water resources, as well as the protection of agroecological systems, are the main

conditions for supporting agricultural production and human life. The lack of developed theoretical and methodological bases for solving the problems of reforming the state water use management in the study of the problem, the lack of a system for assessing the effectiveness of the use of the water resource potential of the region indicate the imperfection of economic relations in the field of water use. The problem of compliance with national interests and their protection in the use of transboundary water resources of the Aral Sea basin is of particular relevance for the Central Asian countries. The following figures should also be taken into account in water management issues. The situation with water shortage in our region is getting more complicated every year. Over the past 10 years, for example, the volume of water in Uzbekistan has decreased by 12 percent, and this year compared to 2019- by 15 percent. The energy and water costs required for cotton and grain production are also high. 2.5 million hectares are irrigated by more than 5 thousand pumps, which is 8 billion kilowatt-hours of energy and 2.4 trillion soums of budget funds are spent. On average, 800 thousand soums are spent on the supply of water by pumps per hectare from the budget. About 5-6 ml of water per year with surface irrigation. a cubic meter or 20 percent of water is wasted[1].

In the course of the lesson, students should also master: participation in the design of water supply and sanitation systems; determination of the approximate consumption of natural and waste water; development of technological schemes for water treatment; establishment of compliance of design solutions with environmental requirements; management of water supply and sanitary networks and structures; compliance with technological modes of operation of environmental protection structures, waste water, compliance with environmental standards and regulations; development of the technological process of natural and waste water treatment;; to control the quality of natural and waste water, it is necessary to learn how to conduct chemical and microbiological analyses.

Centralized water supply supplies water through a water supply system to several points of demand, which are a complex of engineering structures used to

carry out water intake from a water source necessary to ensure its quality in accordance with the requirements of the water user, to supply the water flow to the place of consumption and distribution among users. The quality of drinking water in our country is regulated by the Uzst.

In a decentralized local water supply, the analysis of water by the population is carried out directly from the water source, without a distribution network of pipelines. As a source of water supply, underground water is most often used, and water from mine wells or springs is used. Sanitary regulations allow the use for drinking purposes of water with a coli-index of no more than 10, turbidity on the standard scale of no more than 5 mg/l, purity of no more than 30 cm (according to the Snellen font), color no more than 30°

The water supply- system is a complex of structures for the quality supply of water to a certain (given) group of consumers (this object) in the required amount. In addition, the water supply system must have a certain degree of reliability, that is, to ensure the supply of water to consumers without an unacceptable decrease in the specified performance indicators in terms of the quantity or quality of the supplied water. The water supply system must ensure the supply of water from natural sources, its purification and supply to the places of consumption, if this follows from the requirements of consumers. Depending on local environmental conditions and the nature of water consumption, as well as economic considerations, water supply and its components can vary greatly. Water supply systems can be classified according to a number of basic characteristics.

By purpose: water supply systems of settlements(cities, towns), water supply production, agricultural water supply systems, fire alarm systems and water supply, combined water supply systems (economic-production, economic-fire protection, etc.).).

Method of water supply: gravity (gravity) with a mechanical flow of water (pumps), quenching (in some places gravity, in other pumps).

According to the method of using natural resources: those that receive water from surface sources (river, lake, etc.), those that receive water from underground sources (Spring, artesian, etc.), of a mixed type.

According to the method of water use: once-through the water supply system (with a single use of water), water reuse systems.

Drinking water -supply is a set of measures to provide the population with drinking water. Drinking water supply includes the selection and evaluation of possible sources of water supply, the choice of the location and construction of water intake facilities, the sanitary assessment of water and measures to protect them from pollution.

When choosing a source of water supply, first of all, the established need for drinking water and the presence of surface or fresh underground water in the territory are taken into account. From the point of view of water quality and protection from pollution, preference is given to groundwater. When selecting a source of surface water supply, an assessment of hydrology, conditions, minimum and average water consumption, their compliance with the target water consumption, sanitary characteristics of the basin, industrial development, the availability and possibility of internal, industrial and agricultural sources of pollution in the area of future water intake is carried out. In the event of a discrepancy between the coordination structure of the sanitary and epidemiological service and the requirements of the water source for the properties of drinking water, the necessary quality is ensured (filtration, coagulation, disinfection, etc.).

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8 саноат корхоналарида энергетик аудит ўтказиш орқали электр энергиядан рационал фойдаланиш бўйича тавсиялар ишлаб чиқиш. **Нуров .Ҳ. И, Амруллаев**

9. Контроллерли энергия тежамкор электр юритмалардан фойдаланиш орқали энергия тежаш усуллари ишлаб чиқиш Жумаев А. А Амруллаев Б.Б